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A CLINICO-HISTOPATHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS AND BACILLARY INDEX IN SKIN BIOPSY OF LEPROSY – A STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction:

Leprosy is one of the leading causes of physical disabilities contributing to intense social stigmata resulting in human discrimination. This chronic infectious disease caused by Mycobacterium leprae principally affects skin and peripheral nerve. It can also include muscle, eyes, bones, testis and internal organs. Histopathology study and bacillary index is important in understanding the disease progression, diagnosis, varied manifestation and complications.

Method:

All cases attending the Skin OPD were examined clinically and skin biopsy specimen was obtained from clinically diagnosed cases of Leprosy and stained with Hematoxylin & Eosin and modified Fite Faraco (AFB). The clinical diagnosis correlated with histopathology in all 100 cases.

Results:

The age of the patients was ranged from 4 to 80 years. The male to female ratio of patients was 3 to 1. Borderline Tuberculoid was the most common presentation. Highest parity was observed in BT and Histoid leprosy. Clinico-histopathological agreement was seen in 76 (76%) cases.

Conclusion:

The clinical and histopathological features along with bacteriological index are useful than any single parameter in arriving definitive diagnosis and classification of the leprosy.

Key words: HISTOPATHOLOGY, BACILLARY INDEX, SKIN BIOPSY, LEPROSY

INTRODUCTION:

One of the oldest illnesses known to man is leprosy, sometimes referred to as Hansen's disease. Leprosy continues to be a significant public health issue throughout much of Asia, including in India. Even though leprosy was declared eradicated nationwide in January 2006, the illness is still widespread in numerous states of our nation. In 2009, there were 2, 27, 849 estimated new cases diagnosed worldwide, of which 1, 33,717 (58.7%) were detected in India.

Leprosy can manifest in a variety of clinicopathological ways, depending on the host's immunological condition. Leprosy can be diagnosed using a number of techniques, such as a thorough clinical examination of the skin lesions and peripheral nerves, a histological section, and a modified Fite Faraco test to demonstrate the presence of bacilli. The five forms of leprosy identified by Ridley and Jopling are Tuberculoid Leprosy (TT), Borderline Tuberculoid Leprosy (BT), Mid-Borderline Leprosy (BB), Borderline Lepromatous Leorosity (BL), and Lepromatous Leprosy (LL). Their classification suggests an immunological foundation for leprosy. This classification is widely acknowledged and strongly advised.

Significant differences are observed in the interpretation of these hypopigmented skin

lesions both clinically and histopathologically, despite the fact that the clinical diagnosis is founded on distinctive hypopigmented patches with sensory loss. Therefore, skin biopsy is crucial to the diagnosis of leprosy, in addition to the bacilloscopic examination and the comprehensive clinical information that is presented. A histopathological examination also aids in determining the patient's immunological condition, which allows us to forecast how the patient will react to treatment. The purpose of this study is to examine the relationships between leprosy patients' clinical and histopathological diagnoses and to assess the value of skin biopsies in leprosy diagnosis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A descriptive analytical investigation has been conducted at the SBKS MI&RC Pathology Department, Dhiraj Hospital. After obtaining their agreement, at least one hundred leprosy patients of all sexes and all age groups were chosen at random and added to the research. As per the conventional protocol followed for assessing a patient with leprosy, a comprehensive general and local examination was performed in each patient after obtaining a full history. All patients had the appropriate examinations. With the patient's permission, a skin sample was performed in each case for histological analysis.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Skin biopsies taken from patients who have been clinically diagnosed as either newly diagnosed leprosy cases or long-standing cases that are not improving with treatment.

- All patient ages who are clinically suspect of having leprosy are included.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Skin biopsies taken from patients who have been clinically diagnosed as either newly diagnosed leprosy cases or long-standing cases that are not improving with treatment.
- All patient ages who are clinically suspect of having leprosy are included.

In addition to noting presenting problems such skin lesions, numbness, trophic ulcers, and deformities, a thorough medical history including age, sex, employment, and socioeconomic status was obtained.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

Each patient underwent a thorough general checkup. Local skin lesion examination was performed, paying specific attention to satellite lesions, supplying nerves, quantity, shape, size, surface, borders, feeling, hair loss, sweat loss, and trophic changes. We palpated each peripheral nerve to check for pain and swelling. Clinical diagnoses for the patients included Tuberculoid Leprosy (TT), Borderline Tuberculoid Leprosy (BT), Mid-Borderline Leprosy (BB), Borderline Lepromatous Leorosis (BL), and Lepromatous Leprosy (LL).

ROUTINE INVESTIGATIONS

Every patient was routinely examined using tests for HIV using ELISA, Hb%, total count, differential count, ESR, platelet count, bleeding time, and clotting time.

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EXAMINATION

Skin biopsy¹

The value of a skin biopsy

- To aid in management
- To establish the diagnosis
- To categorize leprosy
- To detect complications such responses

Following the patient's written agreement, the dermatologist took punch biopsies of the skin for the research, which were then sent in 10% formalin to the department of pathology. Following a sufficient 8–12 hours of fixation, the samples were processed according to standard procedure. A 5-micron-thick paraffin embedded slice was then stained with hematoxylin and eosin for morphological examination.

Sections of skin biopsies stained with hematoxylin and eosin will be analyzed for the following:

1. Epidermal atrophy
2. Granulomas of epitheloid and macrophage cells
3. The quantity and distribution of foam cells, histiocytes, and lymphocytes
4. Nerve, blood vascular, and adnexal infiltration
5. Grenz Zone.

In every instance, sections stained with Modified Fite's stain will be checked for Acid Fast Bacilli. Based on the Ridley and Jopling Scale, the histopathological results will be categorized as Polar Tuberculoid (TT), Borderline Tuberculoid (BT), Mid- Borderline (BB), Borderline Lepromatous (BL), and Polar Lepromatous (LL).

Site

The biopsy should be collected from the center of the lesion, where it is active, in cases of ambiguous leprosy. In the event that there are several lesions, the lesion that is most active will be chosen, and a biopsy will be obtained from its margin.

Size

A 1.5 cm long by 0.6 cm broad elliptical section of skin that is subcutis and dermis deep will be removed.

Fixatives

- Lowy's fixative (FMA)
- 100 ml of formaldehyde (40%)
- 20 g of magnesium chloride
- 30 ml of glacial acetic acid
- 1000 ml of diluted water

After two hours in this solution, the biopsy material should be moved to 70% ethyl alcohol, where it may be preserved for a long period. The subsequent stains are completed:

- Fite - Faraco stain
- Immunochemical stain
- Gomari methanamine silver stain
- Haematoxyline and eosin stain
- S-100 stain

Every clinically confirmed case of leprosy had a skin biopsy specimen, which was stained using the following methods

- Hematoxylin and Eosin stain
- Modified Fite's stain
- The process for staining slides with hematoxylin and eosin involves soaking them in alcohol for two minutes after the paraffin is removed
- wiped with water
- Hematoxylin staining for 15 minutes, followed by a water wash
- Absolute alcohol was given one or two dips in water.
- For three minutes, counterstain with 1% aqueous eosin.
- Dehydrated
- mounted using DPX

Modified Fite's stain - to show the morphology, location, and quantity of AFB

RESULTS:

Incidence of Clinical diagnosis

In our study all the patients were thoroughly examined clinically and diagnosed.

Out of 100 cases,

TABLE 1: Incidence of CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS

Clinical diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Tuberculoid leprosy	04	4.0
Borderline Tuberculoid	39	39.0
Mid Borderline	4	4.0
Borderline Lepromatous	20	20.0
Lepromatous leprosy	21	21.0
Histoid leprosy	3	3.0
Erythema Nodosum Leprosum	9	9.0
Total	100	100.0

Incidence of Histopathological distribution

In our study skin biopsy was taken from all the 100 patients and stained with H & E stain. Out of 100 patients 26(26%) patients were histologically diagnosed as Inconclusive to Leprosy and its variants.

TABLE 2: Incidence of HISTOPATHOLOGICAL DISTRIBUTION

Histopathological diagnosis	Frequency	Percent
TUBERCULOID LEPROSY	4	4.0
BORDERLINE TUBERCULOID	30	30.0
MID BORDERLINE	3	3.0
BORDERLINE LEPROMATOUS	12	12.0
LEPROMATOUS LEPROSY	16	16.0
HISTOID LEPROSY	4	4.0
ENL	5	5.0
INCONCLUSIVE	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Age Distribution

In our study, the youngest patient was 4 years old and the eldest was 80 years old.

The maximum number of patients (36%) showing clinical activity in this study belonged to the 21- 30 years' age group whereas the least number of patients (2%) belonged to the less than 10 years age group.

TABLE 3: AGE DISTRIBUTION

Age	Frequency	Percentage
0 – 10	02	02
11- 20	16	16
21- 30	36	36
31- 40	17	17
41- 50	13	13
51- 60	10	10

ABOVE 61	06	06
TOTAL	100	100

Sex distribution

In the present study, male patients comprised 75 % and female patients comprised 25% of the total patients. Male to female ratio was 3:1

TABLE 4: SEX DISTRIBUTION

Sex distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Male	75	75.0
Female	25	25.0
Total	100	100.0

Duration

Minimum duration of clinical presentation of disease was 2 days and maximum was 5years.

- Maximum number of patients 65 i.e., 65% in this study had the disease duration of less than 1year
- Duration was between 1-5 years in 33(33%)
- More than 5 years in 2(2%).

TABLE 5 : DURATION of Clinical Presentation

Duration	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 YEAR	65	65.0
1 TO 5 YEAR	33	33.0
> 5 YEAR	2	2.0

Complaints

In this study out of 100 patients, 51(51%) patients had the complaints of hypopigmented skin lesion. 36(36%) patients had raised lesions. Numbness & hypopigmented lesions in 8(8%) patients and swelling & hypopigmented lesions in 5(5%) patients.

TABLE 6: COMPLAINTS

COMPLAINTS	Frequency	Percentage
Hypopigmented lesions	51	51.0
Raised lesion	36	36.0
Hypopigmented lesions & Numbness	8	8.0
Hypopigmented lesions & swelling	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Site distribution of skin lesions

In our study among 100 patients, majority of patients had lesions over trunk. 38(38%) on trunk, 23(23%) cases had lesions on upper limbs, 24(24%) on the lower limb, 14(14%) on the head & neck, 1(1%) patients had lesions over multiple sites of body.

TABLE 7: SITE DISTRIBUTION

Site	Frequency	Percent
TRUNK	38	38.0

LOWER LIMB	24	24.0
UPPER LIMB	23	23.0
HEAD & NECK	14	14.0
MULTIPLE SITES	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Acid fast bacilli

In our study 30(30%) patients showed smear positivity whereas 70(70%) showed smear negativity. 2 (6.66%) BT patient, 7 (23.33%) BL, 16 (53.33%) LL, 3 (10%) Histoid and 2(6.66%) ENL patient showed smear positivity. All Tuberculoid patients were smear negative.

TABLE 8: AFB

AFB	Frequency	Percentage
NEGATIVE	70	70.0
POSITIVE	30	30.0
Total	100	100.0

Bacillary index:

In this study out of 30 AFB smear positive cases, 20% of smear positive patients had BI less than and equal to 3+ and 80% of patients had more than 3+ of BI.

TABLE 9: BACILLARY INDEX

BACTERIAL INDEX	Frequency	Percentage
< or = 3+	6	20
>3+	24	80
TOTAL	30	100

TABLE 10: AFB stain and histopathological correlation

AFB stain	HISTOPATHOLOGICAL DAIGNOSIS								Total
	TT	BT	BB	BL	LL	Histoid	ENL	Inconclusive	
Positive	0 0%	2 2%	0 0%	7 7%	15 15%	4 4.0%	2 2.0%	0 0%	30 30%
Negative	4 4.0%	28 28.0%	3 3.0%	5 5.0%	1 1%	0 0.0%	3 3.0%	26 26%	70 70.0%
Total	4 4.0%	30 30.0%	3 3.0%	12 12.0%	16 16.0%	4 4.0%	5 5.0%	26 26%	100 100.0%

TABLE 11: AFB Stain and clinical Diagnosis

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS	

AFB	TT	BT	BB	BL	LL	HISTOID	ENL	TOTAL
POSITIVE	0	5	0	11	9	2	3	30
	0%	5%	0%	11%	9%	2%	3%	30%
NEGATIVE	4	34	4	9	12	1	6	70
	4%	34%	4%	9%	12%	1%	6%	70%
Total	4	39	4	20	21	3	9	100
	4%	39%	4%	20%	21%	3%	9%	100.0%

Out of total histopathological diagnosed AFB stained smear, Histoid Leprosy and Lepromatous leprosy show highest percentage of AFB positivity, 100% and 93.75% respectively.

Table 12: Comparison Table of clinical and Histopathological diagnosis

Types of leprosy	Clinical Diagnosis	Histopathological Diagnosis							INCONCLUSIVE	Correlation with clinical type %
		TT	BT	BB	BL	LL	ENL	HISTOID		
TT	04	2% (2)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	2% (2)	50%
BT	39	1% (1)	24% (24)	1% (1)	1% (1)	2% (2)	0% (0)	0% (0)	10% (10)	61.53%
BB	04	0% (0)	0% (0)	1% (1)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	3% (3)	25%
BL	20	0% (0)	3% (3)	0% (0)	10% (10)	4% (4)	0% (0)	1% (1)	2% (2)	50%
LL	21	1% (1)	2% (2)	1% (1)	1% (1)	9% (9)	0% (0)	1% (1)	6% (6)	42.85%
ENL	09	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	1% (1)	5% (5)	0% (0)	3% (3)	55.55%
HISTOID	03	0% (0)	1% (1)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	2% (2)	0% (0)	66.66%
TOTAL	100	4% (4)	30% (30)	3% (3)	12% (12)	16% (16)	5% (5)	4% (4)	26% (26)	74%

TT-TUBERCULOID LEPROSY; BT-BORDERLINE TUBERCULOID LEPROSY MIDBORDERLINE LEPROSY; BL-BORDERLINE LEPROMATOUS LEPROSY; LL-LEPROMATOUS LEPROSY; IL-INDETERMINATE LEPROSY

Clinico-histopathological agreement was seen in 74 (74%) cases and disagreement in 26 (26%) cases.

Out of 4 patients clinically diagnosed as TT, 2(50%) patients had histopathological correlation. Out of 39 patients clinically diagnosed as BT, 24 (61.53%) patients had histopathological correlation. Remaining 15 patient turned out to be 1% as TT, 1% as BB, 1% as BL, 2% as LL and 10% as non-conclusive to leprosy respectively. Out of 4 patients clinically diagnosed as BB only 1(25%) patient had histological correlation, out of 20 patients clinically diagnosed as BL, 10(50%) patients had histopathological correlation, out of 21 patients clinically diagnosed as LL, 09(42.85%) patients had histopathological correlation, out of 3 patients clinically diagnosed as Histoid leprosy, 02(66.66%) patient had histopathological correlation, out of 9

patients clinically diagnosed as Lepra reaction, 05(55.55%) patient had histopathological correlation.

DISCUSSION:

In the present study, Ridley-Jopling classification was used to classify leprosy histopathologically in all cases. Indeterminate leprosy was not included for analysis. Histoid leprosy is considered as a variant of Lepromatous leprosy and it was included in LL spectrum.

Age Distribution

In the **present study** more number of patients belong to the age group of 21-30 years (**36%**). In a study done by **Moorthy BN et al**², majority of patients were between 20-29 years (20.70%).

Singh et al³, found the disease in 48% of patients belonging to age group of 21- 40 years.

Santaram and Porichha⁴ found majority of patients were 21- 40 years.

Similarly, **Jindal et al**⁵ and Samuel et al⁷ found the disease in 48% of patients belonging to the age group of 21- 40 years.

Thus the age incidence in the present study correlates well with the other studies. The disease is more common in this age group because of their mobility and increased opportunity for contacts.

Sex Distribution

In the **present study**, **75%** of patients were males and **25%** were females. Similarly, **Santaram and Porichha** found the disease in 80% of males.

Singh et al³ found the disease in 69% of males.

Similarly, **Moorthy et al**², **Gridhar M et al**⁶ and **Nitesh Mohan et al**⁸ found the disease to be more common in males.

The result of the present study is close to the above-mentioned studies with regard to the sex. This disease is more common in males because of their outdoor works and higher chances of getting infection.

Duration

The duration of illness in the **present study** was less than 1 year in 65% of patients, 1-5 years in 33% and more than 5 years in 2% of patients.

Similarly, **Ramanjanayalu**¹⁰ found the duration of illness was less than 6 months in 54% of patients, 1-5 years in 24% and 6-11 months in 17% of patients.

Wim et al¹⁰, found the duration was up to 6 months in 30% of patients, 7-12 months in 32%, 13-24 months in 17%, 25-36 in 9.3%, 37- 60 months in 6.3% and more than 60 months in 5.4%.

Thus most of the patients had the illness for the duration of less than 1 year. This is because of the patients present to the hospital earlier.

Complaints

In **this study** out of 100 patients, 51(51%) patients had the complaints of Hypopigmented skin lesion.36(36%) patients had Raised lesions, Numbness & Hypopigmented lesions in 8(8%) patients and swelling & hypopigmented lesions in 5(5%) patients.

Similarly, **Nitesh Mohan et al**⁹ found that most common clinical presentation was hypopigmented patch (61.58%) followed by erythematous plaque or nodule (38.42%). This also correlated well with study done by **M Gridhar et al, Ocampo and Francisco**.

Hypopigmented anesthetic skin lesion is one of the cardinal signs of leprosy.

Site of lesion

In the **present study**1% of patients had the lesions over multiple body sites, 23% had the lesions on upper limbs and 14% of patients had lesions on head and neck region.

But in the study done by **Nitesh Mohan et al**⁹, 34.21% of patients had the lesion on upper limbs, 21.05% of patients had on head& neck site and 15.79% on multiple sites.

There are no many available studies to compare this parameter.

Clinical diagnosis

In the **present study**, out of 100 patients, 39% were diagnosed as BT, 21% as LL, 20% as BL, 4% as TT and 4% as BB, 3% as histoid leprosy and 9% as ENL.

Nitesh Mohan et al found BT in 45.26%, LL in 23.68%, BL in 13.68%, TT in 7.89% and BB in 2.12% of patients.

Similarly, **Ramanjanayalu**⁹ and **Zhongdong**¹¹ found that majority of patients had BT.

Jindal et al⁵ found LL in 33%, BT in 28%, BL in 23%, TT in 5.5% and BB in 4% of patients.

Vara and Marfatiya¹² found BT in 36%, LL in 52%, TT in 13%, BB in 9% and BL and pure neuritic in 8%.

Thus the results in the present study correlate well with other studies and most common clinical type was Borderline Tuberculoid.

Acid fast bacilli

In the **present study** 30% of patients showed smear positivity and 70% of patients showed smear negativity. Smear positivity was less than 3+ in 20% of patients and more than 3+ in 80% of patients.

All TT patients were smear negative. 5% of BT patients were smear positive.

Ramanjanayalu⁹ found overall positivity in 39% of patients and negativity in 60% of patients.

Vara and Marfatiya¹² found positivity in 38% of patients.

In the study of **Vara**¹³, smear positivity was less than 3+ in 28% of patients and more than 3+ in 18% of patients. Smear negativity in 54% of patients.

The smear positivity in the present study is more than above mentioned studies. This is probably because of clinical typing of patients.

Histopathological distribution

In **our study** 30% of patients histopathologically diagnosed as BT patients, 16% as LL, 12% as BL, 3% as BB and 4% as TT, 4% as histoid leprosy, 5% as ENL, 26 % as inconclusive.

Similarly, **Nitesh Mohan et al**⁸ found 44.4% as BT, 19.05% as LL, 14.8% as IL, 12.7% as BL, 7.4% as TT and 1.6% as BB.

In the study of **Manandhar et al**¹⁴, 40% of patients histopathologically diagnosed as BT.

Thus histologically, the common classification made was Borderline Tuberculoid.

Clinico-histopathological correlation

In our study skin biopsy was done in all 100 patients.

Clinico-histopathological agreement was seen in 74 (74%) cases and disagreement in 26 (26%) cases.

Out of 4 patients clinically diagnosed as TT, 2(50%) patients had histopathological correlation.

Out of 39 patients clinically diagnosed as BT, 24 (61.53%) patients had histopathological correlation. There was complete agreement between the clinical and histopathologic diagnosis in 60% of the cases.

Out of 4 patients clinically diagnosed as BB only one (25%) patient had histological correlation.

Out of 20 patients clinically diagnosed as BL, 10(50%) patients had histopathological correlation.

Out of 21 patients clinically diagnosed as LL, (42.85%) patients had histopathological correlation.

TABLE 13: Clinico-pathological correlation in various spectrum in various studies

Types of leprosy	Mohan et al	Manandhar et al	Moorthy BN et al	Nadkarni NS et al	Kar et al	Kalla et al	Jerath & Desai	Present study
TT	71.93	24	46.15	97	87.5	75.6	74.5	50
BT	79.76	63.15	66.66	95	60.9	44.2	64.7	61.53
BB	66.67	0	50	89	54.5	37	28.5	25
BL	66.67	57.14	70	87	53.8	43.7	53.8	50
LL	97.22	57.14	80	98	71.4	76.7	61.5	42.85
IL	50	0	20	-	81.2	-	88.8	-

Different studies observed highest percentage of clinicopathological correlation of Lepromatous leprosy and Tuberculoid leprosy in their studies and showed least clinic-pathological correlation in mid-borderline lepromatous leprosy.

In contrast to our study, Nayak SV et al¹⁵ study showed maximum correlation in mid-Borderline (100%).

Ridley and Jopling¹⁶ found complete agreement between clinical and histopathological types in 68.3%.

There was a minor disagreement (disagreement in one group) in 26 (26%) cases and no major disagreement (more than one group). Ridley and Jopling¹⁶, found minor disagreement in 21 patients (25.6%), major disagreement in 5 patients (6%).

The variation in different studies may be due to different criteria used to select the cases and difference in number of cases of each type. Various factors also influence the histopathological diagnosis such as differences in sample size, choosing the biopsy site, age of the lesion and immunological status of the patient at the time of biopsy.

CONCLUSION:

In this study,

- The higher incidence in the age group 21-30 years.
- The incidence was higher in males because of their more physical activity and thus more chances of getting infection.
- The duration of illness was less than one year in majority of patients.
- Most common complaint was hypopigmented skin lesions.
- The higher number of patients were Borderline Tuberculoid. This is because, these patients come early for the treatment because of its neurological symptoms.
- AFB positivity was found in 30% of patients.
- Clinico-histopathological correlation was seen in 74% of the patients. Maximum correlation was observed in Borderline Tuberculoid leprosy.

In conclusion it can be said Leprosy still continues to be a domestic, national, global burden and is present in different clinico-pathological forms.

Many cases can be diagnosed clinically; especially Lepromatous pole of the disease, however, other types of Leprosy pose a significant problem in clinical diagnosis. Histopathological examination of the lesions confirms the exact subtype of the disease and facilitate the institution of accurate mode of therapy. So, correlation of clinical and histopathological features along

with bacteriological index is more useful for accurate typing of leprosy than considering single parameter alone.

CONSENT: As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

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